

PRELIMINARY RESULTS OF RECENT STUDIES ON MYXOMYCETES IN CHERNOMORSKYI BIOSPHAERE RESERVE (UKRAINE)

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Until recently the information on the myxomycete biodiversity of deserts and dry steppes was limited by the data from those specific biotopes of USA and Mongolia (Blackwell, Gilbertson, 1984; Novozhilov, Golubeva, 1986). However, from the beginning of XXI century the regular studies of myxomycetes on territories with arid climate were started in Russia and Kazakhstan (Zemlianskaia, 2003; Novozhilov et al., 2007). Unfortunately, the myxomycetes of Ukrainian steppe zone which covers about 40% of the total area of the country continue to be largely neglected.

During a week in October 2006 we carried out the first preliminary survey for myxomycete species in Chernomorskyi biosphaere reserve which is situated in the southern part of Ukrainian steppe zone (Kherson and Mykolaiv obl.) at the shore of Black Sea. Investigation of myxomycetes was realized on the territories of two reserve divisions - Ivano-Rybalchanske and Solonoozerne. Although the principal type of vegetation on the investigated reserve plots is represented by sandy steppes with grass dominants from the genera *Artemisia*, *Festuca*, *Koeleria*, *Agropyron* etc. the intrazonal woodland biotops were chosen for myxomycete specimens collecting. The forest vegetation was occupied the hollows, so called "pods", which are formed on depressive elements of reserve relief with the high level (above 1,5 m) of soil water. Those forests named according to the local term as "haiki" are mainly composed of *Betula borysthena* Klokov, *Quercus robur* L., *Populus tremula* L., *Ailanthus altissima* (Mill.) Swingle, and etc. They are rather rich with suitable for myxomycetes substrates: woody debris, bark, leaf litter.

In the frame of the present work we found 15 species of classes Ceratiomyxomycetes and Myxomycetes from 10 genera, 6 families and 5 orders. In reserve the first class was represented by one species *Ceratiomyxa fruticulosa* (O.F. Mill) T. Macbr. belonging to the order Ceratiomyxales. Among the orders of class Myxomycetes, the Physarales included 6 species collected in the reserve (*Didymium squamulosum* (Alb. & Schw.) Fr., *Fuligo candida* Pers., *F. septica* (L.) F.H. Wigg., *Mucilago crustacea* F.H. Wigg., *Physarum album* (Bull.) Chevall, *Ph. globuliferum* (Bull.) Pers.), the Liceales (*Lycogala epidendrum* (L.) Fr., *Tubulifera arachnoidea* (Batsch) Gmel., *T. microsperma* Berk. & M.A. Curtis) and the Stemonitales (*Diachea leucopodia* (Bull.) Rostaf., *Stemonitis axifera* (Bull.) T. Macbr., *S. splendens* Rostaf.) – 3 species in each, the Trichiales – 2 species only (*Arcyria denudata* (L.) Wettst., *A. obvellata* (Oeder) Onsberg). All of the species are considered new records for Chernomorskyi biosphaere reserve. Among them there are a few rare species for the Left-bank Ukraine: *Didymium squamulosum* (Alb. & Schw.) Fr., *Fuligo candida* Pers. and *Tubulifera microsperma* Berk. & M.A. Curtis were known before for the Left-bank Ukraine only from National nature park "Gomol'schanski forests" (Leontyev, 2007).

Literature

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